

**EFFICACY OF SEASONAL THERMAL FLUCTUATIONS HINDERS
THE SECRETORY BEHAVIOUR OF THE CEREBRAL
NEUROSECRETORY ELEMENTS IN *LYMNAEA (RADIX) LUTEOLA*
WITH PARTICULAR REFERENCE TO ACETONE - SUDAN BLACK B
(ASSB)**

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ABSTRACT

The investigation reveals the adoption of method Acetone Sudan Black B (ASBB) yields a good positive result of the cerebral ganglionic neurosecretory elements of *Lymnaea (Radix) luteola* exposed to various temperatures. Incidentally a good positive intensity of the stain is being elicited when the animals are kept in the different fluctuating temperature regimes ([low (4°C, 10°C), near ambient (20°C, 25°C) and high (30°C, 35°C)] on their secretory dynamics. Concomitant with this, the histochemical nature of the neurosecretory material has also been recorded. In all the profiles of study individuals exposed to near ambient temperature are being considered as normal. And finally, the histochemical analyses are made under different temperature regies on the cerebral neurosecretory elements to ascertain correlative biochemical changes.

KEYWORDS: Acetone – Acetone Sudan Black B (ASBB), Neurosecretory materials (NSM), Secretory dynamics, Pal

Kovit's formula, Hypo-Hyper & Near ambient temperatures.

INTROUCTION

Bound lipid components of Neurosecretory materials (NSM) probes to be ubiquitous and possibly the term Myelinated neurons are apparently applied in both vertebrates and invertebrates. Several investigators successfully demonstrated the lipid compound in the NSM in several invertebrates with adoption of Acetone - Sudan Black B method. Histochemical analyses of the secretory material in the said ganglion are made to assess the biochemical nature of the elaboration.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The materials, used in the present investigation are full grown *Lymnaea* (*Radix*) *luteola* (size ranging from 1.2 cm 1.5 cm), were collected from an adjoining pond within Vivekananda college (Thakurpukur) campus during monsoon. These individuals are kept in suitable plastic containers filled with same pond water. Periodic renewal of pond water was practised in course of their maintenance and acclimation.

Subjection to thermal exposures has been monitored according to the schedule for experimentation. Indeed, near ambient temperature (20°C and 25°C) treated individuals were considered to be the normal. However, hyper & hypothermic—30⁰ to 35⁰C as well 4⁰ to 10⁰C are also maintained. Hence, these animals were put into a separate B.O.D. chambers where the aforesaid temperature regimes are being maintained precisely.

HISTOPHYSIOLOGICAL STUDIES

Investigations were made on the basis of staining intensities, of features morphological stainable granules, their quantity and distribution, size of the cell bodies and nuclei in terms of volume determination by using Palkovit's formula (1963). The activity of the cells in question were assessed as per the formulation devised by Hartwick-nucleoplasamic indices (Np index)-cited by De Roberties (1968). Incidentally, the cells of either large or medium dimensions are taken into account for the diagnosis of their criteria.

GENERAL HISTOCHEMISTRY

Acetone - Sudan Black B (ASBB) method (Berenbaum, 1954) for detection of bound lipid. Fixative- Carney's fluid.

OBSERVATIONS

Acetone - Sudan Black B (ASBB)

1. HYPOTHERMAL EXPOSURE

AT 4°C

Majority of the neurosecretory elements display a good positive reaction for masked lipid. Nuclei are conspicuous and the cytoplasm remains distributed with bound lipid positive material as aggregates. In any case, the morphological characteristics of the neurosecretory particles are hard to diagnose. Presence of this material at the axonal region is not so revealing but their concentration at the axon-hillock portion is not ruled out.

AT 10°C

The neurosecretory cells show marked positive reaction. The nuclei, when visible, are bright black. Sometimes, the disposition of bound lipid positive material within the cytoplasm is so dense that the Identity of granular consistency of secretory material is rather Inconceivable (Fig. 38). These criteria are especially noticeable in case of cells of larger dimension. Time to time clumping of bound lipid positive material may be observed and is more spectacular for large to medium types of cell. Axona 1 processes of smaller lension may have the clumped material along their courses.

Fig. 1: Section showing neurosecretory cells with positive reaction for bound lipid. Note distinction of good the nuclei, accumulation of stained material to its vicinity and lack of granular configuration in the secretory substances. X 532.

2. EXPOSURE TO NEAR AMBIENT TEMPERATURE

AT 20°C

Pattern of distribution of bound lipid substances in the neuro-secretory elements does not differ much. Only characteristic difference may be encountered in case of the cells containing ill-defined nuclei and less reactive nucleoli (Fig. 39). Furthermore, extent of accumulation of bound lipid positive material within the perikarya, be large or small, is not much conceivable. Axonal processes, however, are found to contain these material and may be traceable. (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2: Bound lipid positive neurosecretory elements showing ill-defined nucleoli, clumped secretory material and presence of occasional axonal transport. X 532

AT 25°C

Bound lipid positive reaction of the nuclei is less but the nucleoli are prominent because of their deep black colouration. A gradation in the secretory nature of the neurosecretory cell complements is obvious (Fig. 3) and, accordingly, deep to moderate reaction has been recorded. Majority of the small cells have, however, show Intense bound lipid positive reaction than the larger ones.

Fig. 3: Section showing variable masked lipid contents within the neurosecretory complements. Note intense reaction to cells of smaller dimension and prominence of nucleoli. X 532.

3. HYPERTHERMAL EXPOSURE

AT 30°C

Bound lipid positive reaction is explicit. And the cytoplasm remains engorged with granules which are either deep brown or black. Disposition of bound lipid positive material does not register, 'clumping condition. In general, the nuclei are conspicuous besides possessing bound lipid positive chromatin granules (Fig. 4). Sometimes accumulation of black granules at the axon-hillock region is not ruled out.

Fig. 4: Section showing explicit reaction for acetone-Sudan black-B amongst the neurosecretory elements. Note distinction of the nuclei along with the nucleoli and near uniform staining response of the cytoplasm. X 532.

AT 35°C

Localisation of masked lipid in majority of the neurosecretory elements is not there occurs fluctuation in their Intensity. The nuclei, too, are conspicuous; cytoplasm ordinarily so difficult but have rich distribution of masked lipids but this is more spectacular in case of large to medium types of cell. Axonal processes sometimes show bound lipid positive granules but their intensity gradually wanes at the distal regions (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Section showing distribution of masked lipid positive substances within the neurosecretory perikarya well as along the axonal processes. Note lack of granular conformity coupled with overall deformity in the cell outline. X 532.

Table 1: Showing alterations in the histochemical profiles of cerebral neurosecretory cells of *Lymnaea (Radix) luteola* under the variable temperature regimes.

Methods adopted	Reacting sites/groups	Hypothermal		Near Ambient		Hyperthermal	
		4° C	10° C	20°C	25°C	30°C	35°C
Acetone - Sudan Black B (ASBB)	Bound Lipid	+++	+++	+++	+	++	+/-

+/- Doubtful reaction

+/+ / +/+ Reactions of increasing intensity

Series 1,2: Reactions of increasing intensity.

Series 3: Doubtful reaction intensity of Acetone - Sudan Black B (ASBB) reaction is well documented in the Hypothermal and Near Ambient temperatures but in the hyperthermal situation the same intensity dwindles.

DISCUSSION

Localisation of bound lipids in the neurosecretory perikarya, irrespective of the several phyla of invertebrates has been cited in clear terms (Faser, 1959; Ganguly, 1962; Nanda and Goswami, 1978; Sadana and Kaur, 1980; Majumder, 1983; Rajlakshmi Bhanu et al., 1983; Bandyopadhyay, 1987 and Tarafdar, 1988). Negative or very weak intensities of reaction of bound lipid for NSM in some species may be interpreted due to "strong binding" to render the lipoprotein in laminated form (Sjöstrand, 1953) to have a least affinity for the fat-soluble colouring agents by steric hindrances (Berenbaum, 1958) or depends on the acidophilic nature of NSM endowed with protein rich in tyrosine (Boer, 1965). Affinity for bound lipid with neurosecretory elaboration of some molluscs like *L. stagnalis* (Boer, 1965), *Mytilus viridis* (Nagabhushanam, 1974) and *Lamellidens marginalis* (Tarafdar, 1988) is obvious. Necessity for the masked lipid has been highlighted to designate it as "labile barrier" for guarding the neurohormone from various interactions that may develop from different cell constituents (Berenbaum, 1958; Ganguly, 1962; Nanda and Goswami, 1978; Tarafdar, 1988). In the present investigation, the distribution of bound lipid in the cerebral neurosecretory cells of *Lymnaea (Radix) luteola* is in consonance with the observations of Nagabhushanam, 1974 and Tarafdar, 1988. Fluctuation in the distribution of acetone Sudan black B positive material amongst the brain neurosecretory perikarya exposed to three major temperature

regimes has been considered to be linked with the secretory efficacy since role of lipoprotein in the functioning of subcellular organelles like endoplasmic reticulum is noteworthy. In any event, bound lipid moiety of the neurosecretory substances seems to be imperative in the secretory kinetics of the cells concerned (Bhaumik, 1984; Tarafdar, 1988). Near ambient temperature treatment engenders moderate to weak response in contrast with the low temperature exposure which most of the time reflects a good positive reaction. But subjection to high temperature incites very weak to doubtful reaction. Under the circumstances, it may be presumed that role of masked lipid is in a state of disarray following ectothermic stress.

Conclusive Remark

Effects of both high and low thermal exposures encompass some salient changes with respect to the abundance substances, electron dense granules and their disposition within the of heterochromatin microtubular processes, appearances of the cytoplasmic fibrillar elements etc. Such changes from one temperature regime to other provide clues to ascertain the structure-function relationship in the context of the secretory behaviour of the cells concerned. This is especially pertinent when environmental flux in the natural habitat of the species under study is considered (Nanda *et. al.*, 2023, 2024, 2025 & 2026).

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